

An Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis Of Post-Secondary Students' Emotional Responses and Coping Strategies Following Examination Failure of Advanced Level Biology

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Abstract

This paper explores the emotional responses and coping strategies of post-secondary students following their failure in the Advanced Level Biology MATSEC examination, using an Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis (IPA) framework. The study sought to answer three main research questions: (1) What emotional responses do students experience upon failing an important examination? (2) What coping strategies do they adopt to manage these emotions? (3) What forms of support do they consider helpful in preparing for resit exams? Ten Maltese students, aged 17-18, participated in this study, and their experiences were analysed through semi-structured interviews, focus group, and classroom observations. Findings revealed a wide range of emotional responses, with most students experiencing intense feelings of depression, anxiety, and low self-worth, while others exhibited more moderate reactions. The study further found that coping strategies varied significantly. While some students engaged in introspective evaluation and shifted their mindset toward self-improvement, others resorted to avoidance behaviours. Support from family, peers, and teachers emerged as critical, with personalised one-on-one feedback from teachers being highly valued by students. The research, which was guided by Weiner's Attribution Theory, concludes with recommendations for educational leaders and educators to prioritise individualised academic support and continuous professional development for teachers, especially in psychological awareness. Limitations of the study include the short timeframe and the potential for response bias, as the researcher also served as the students' teacher during the remedial course.

Keywords: avoidance behaviour, introspective evaluation, mindset shift, psychology, support networks